

MORE HABITAT FOR INSECTS CAN DELIVER BOTH PUBLIC WELLBEING AND ECONOMIC BENEFITS

Key messages

- ▣ Having more natural enemies of crop pests can improve crop yields.
- ▣ The public gain wellbeing from knowing that bees and beetles are in our environment.
- ▣ People are willing to pay to support insects, including wasps, to exist now and in the future.

The challenge

Previous studies have demonstrated that bees and some other insects are important pollinators of food crops. Other groups of insects, such as wasps, hoverflies and beetles provide additional benefits to farmers; for instance, hoverfly larvae, parasitic wasps and ground beetles can reduce crop pests. Although these pest control services to crops can reduce the need for pesticides, the economic value of this behaviour is unclear.

Beyond farming, many insects, such as butterflies, are important in British culture, but the contribution that they make to our wellbeing, the overall quality of life people experience, including physical health, emotions, and social connections, is poorly understood. Without knowing the costs or benefits of changing insect populations, we may make uninformed decisions that will have negative consequences for both people and nature in the short- or long-term.

Our approach

The DRUID project studied the contribution of insects to crops, and human wellbeing in two ways.

1 THE IMPORTANCE OF NATURAL ENEMIES FOR CROPS

We studied how natural enemy species, like ground beetles, reduce crop pest populations. We then estimated the economic value of crop yields preserved by these natural enemies.

2 THE IMPORTANCE OF INSECTS FOR WELLBEING

We surveyed the UK public about the wellbeing they gain from beetles, bees, wasps, and how this might change in the future.

European paper wasp (*Polistes sp.*) building nest

European paper wasp (*Polistes sp.*)

Our findings

THE IMPORTANCE OF NATURAL ENEMIES FOR CROPS.

We estimated values of UK crop yield losses with contrasting levels of natural enemy numbers. We found that crop protection is highly sensitive to natural enemy pest control, with serious losses of yield where pest control services are weak. Conversely, when there are more natural enemies, they are better able to regulate crop pests and less crop yield is lost.

IMPORTANCE OF INSECTS FOR WELLBEING.

Our survey found that the amount of wellbeing the public get from knowing insects exist and can interact with us, both now and in the future, is dependent on the species.

We gain a lot of wellbeing from bees, and then beetles, but less from wasps. We also gain wellbeing from just knowing that these insects can exist for future generations. We then asked the public how much they valued these insects and found three typical types of people:

- 1 Some were willing to pay a positive amount no matter what insect species it was.**
- 2 Some were not willing to pay anything, and really did not prefer any insect.**
- 3 Many were ambivalent, with positive preferences for bees but less so for beetles or wasps.**

Implications

Natural enemy insects can provide valuable crop-pest regulation services by reducing the pressure of pests on crops, thus increasing yields without the need for high levels of chemical inputs. This can benefit farmers in terms of greater yield, quality and profit, and may also benefit the public through higher quality produce at a lower price.

Most members of the public gained wellbeing from knowing that insects exist now and in the future. Beyond their direct benefits to farming, conserving habitats for these insects to thrive now and in the future could benefit us through improved wellbeing, even if we do not interact with these insects.

Together, these suggest that increasing the population of rural and wild insects may have twin benefits for crops and wellbeing. However, our work also indicates that the evidence base for the economic benefits of insects is scarce, and further work could provide new insights into the specific factors that affect the economic values provided by insects in the UK.

Call to action

We show that bees, beetles, and even wasps can provide economically valuable services that benefit our crops and wellbeing. Stakeholders could help by promoting measures to help rural and farmland insects to thrive and better regulate crop pests. In the context of insecticide resistance and regulations, biological control through insects may be an increasingly attractive option.

King P. et al. (2025) [Economic valuation of pest regulation benefits provided by arthropods in the UK](#). *Ecosystem Services* 76: 101776

This research is part of the DRUID project: <https://druidproject.org.uk/>

